

Use of Types of Art Analysis In Evaluation of Student Knowledge

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Abstract

This article deals with the pedagogical aspects of teaching literature, the pedagogical and psychological basis of the adoption of fiction, thought processes, the types and characteristics of the analysis of fiction in ensuring the continuity, continuity of literary education, ensuring consistency between textbooks.

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Introduction

Person-centered learning technologies allow the learning process to be tailored to the capabilities and needs of learners. The effectiveness of teaching depends on the appropriateness of the educational content and the factors of choosing the right effective teaching methods. In the system of continuing education, it is important to determine the level of mastery of the subjects studied. Assessment of learning outcomes depends on the level of mastery of the content of education. This is because the assessment of students' knowledge is based on the extent to which they have mastered the content of education. In this process, it is necessary to take into account that in the curriculum of each subject in general secondary schools, the content and structure of teaching the subject, the requirements are specified, the leading and auxiliary units of the subject content are given. For example, the leading component for literary science is emotion-value relationships.

Creating a challenging situation in the process of literary education has a great potential in the application of advanced pedagogical technologies to develop the intellectual potential of students.

Problem-based learning develops students' creative thinking potential by developing their independent thinking skills, and lays the foundation for the formation of new knowledge and skills to master them.

In the analysis of the epics "Kuntugmish" in the 8th grade and "Alpomish" in the 9th grade of general secondary schools can be effectively used type of problem-based education. In this case, the text of the epics will be read only after the relevant information about the history of the creation of these epics, the bakhshis who sang it, the copies of the epics.

In the discussion that takes place during the analysis of the works, the students make a logical observation by comparing the problem posed in them with the knowledge they have acquired.

This kind of problematic situation prepares students to understand themselves through the example of the unique adventures experienced by the protagonists of the work, encouraging them to look carefully at any idea. It is still too early to teach work analysis in the middle grades of general secondary schools. Students must go through a complex path to master the basic concepts of literature, with sufficient knowledge to analyze texts in the upper grades. In this regard, several types of analysis of the work of art are important, as well as assess the level of knowledge of students, as well as increase the level of art.

Main part

The cultural direction of the state educational standard in the general secondary education system reflects the following content: "The manifestation of fiction in national and world culture, the interaction of fiction with religion, philosophy, aesthetics, literary criticism, various types of art. Works of national literature and culture are a description of the character of the people. Traditions and innovations in literature and culture. Cultural dialogues, the impact of these dialogues on the literary process. The relationship of literary currents and trends with the various

representatives of art, artists and their aesthetic research. Conducting cultural analysis based on State standards of research on the manifestation of fiction in the context of national culture and world culture.

Linguistic analysis. Linguistics (Latin for "language")

It is a philological science that studies language, the functions, structure, and historical development of language. Based on this feature of linguistics, the researcher M. Shansky formulated his research on the purpose and importance of linguistic analysis. The purpose of linguistic analysis is to record linguistic facts in a literary text, to identify and interpret its significance, and the features of their use. At the same time, special attention should be paid to the extent to which the linguistic features of a literary work are related to literature, language and culture.

Thus, in linguistic analysis, the linguistic material of the text is the basis.

Stylistic analysis. The word "style" is actually a Latin word meaning a writing pen. In the dictionary of literary criticism, the meaning of the word "style" is interpreted as a set of signs that appear in the individual style of the writer, at a certain time, in a direction. If we draw a conclusion based on this definition, stylistic analysis helps to study the author's methods of using language tools, to study the features of the writer's work, to identify the ways in which the writer differs from other writers.

Analyzes

Philological analysis. In explanatory dictionaries, the term "philology" (love of the word) is interpreted in several variants. Based on scientific interpretations and commentaries, philological analysis can be defined as follows: philological analysis is an analysis of the text of a work of art in the study of the writer's language, handwriting (handwriting), writing style.

Contextual analysis. According to the researcher O. Chirkov, a certain amount of context is extracted from the work under contextual analysis and research work is carried out. Contexts can be as follows: 1) a context that reflects a particular historical and literary period (the context must clearly indicate the importance of the work); 2) the context in which the work of a particular writer is reflected (leaving room for the work itself); 3) contexts that reflect certain historical periods (to show that historical periods are fully reflected in a literary work). Contextual analysis always focuses on how detailed the author describes an objective being according to his or her subjective interpretation.

Intertextual analysis. According to the researcher O. Chirkov, in inter-analysis or inter-textual analysis, the features of a work of art are compared (compared) with the features of another work or several other works. As a result of such comparisons, opinions are formed about the peculiarity of the analyzed work, about the author's style, about his worldview reflected in the work. O. Chirkov, a researcher T. Korableva,

develops his views on this subject, highlighting three main types of intertextual relations and explains them as follows:

- 1) citations (quotations) are elements that directly, openly express the connection with known and popular works, textual (textual) connections;
- 2) integral connections, in which reminiscences are conceived by comparing contexts;
- 3) Illusions are similarities, assimilations and parallels (exact similarities) to literary texts in other works.

Thus, quotations, reminiscences, and illusions are determined by intertextual comparisons of the text of the work of art being analyzed. In other words, intertextual analysis requires research that compares the text of a work of art to the original source. Only in this way it is possible to identify the peculiarities of the writer's artistic world in the text covered by the analysis, to compare and contrast the text with similar examples in other works.

Comparative analysis. A study of the examples of word art manifested in a work of art in comparison with similar achievements in other national literatures.

Psychological analysis. Its theoretical basis is the following doctrine: 1) Wundt's (1832 -1920) doctrine of the creative process (this doctrine focuses more on the mental state of the creative person; 2) Z. Freud's (1856 - 1939) doctrine of abstraction (the author himself was the first to study and interpret this direction); 3) The teachings of O. Potebnya (1835 - 1891) (he explains artistic creation as a reflection of the writer's inner world). O. Potebnya introduced the concept of "inner form" of words and images into the science of literature; in creation the word developed a theory of sequence in the form of a myth image, introduced the notion of their difference into scientific consumption, and so on. According to the researcher V. Moklitsa, the work is the result of processes in the inner world of the artist, a mechanism that participates in every component of the work, without being seen. Any work of art we study is a visible part of the iceberg, and the bulk of this work of art lies "hidden" in the web of the author's psyche. By reading the work carefully, we get to the bottom of the creative process, we become aware of the goals set by the author, we know what is the cornerstone of the analysis (foundation) in his work.

Mythological analysis. Almost all literary critics in their research refer to mythology to one degree or another, because fiction itself is directly connected with the science of myths, mythical plots, mythologems and myths in general. If we talk about folklore, folklore samples are created from head to toe on the basis of mythology, which is an emphasis on the mythological constant (constant - foundation, foundation, foundation stone) for their flourishing.

Structural analysis. The structure of the whole, the structure, the internal structure. This type of analysis examines the structural semantic relationships of a

system, an artistic whole, that reflects its contextual connections with the internal structure of a literary work.

Hermeneutic analysis. Hermeneutics is a Greek word meaning “to interpret”, “to explain”. Such an analysis is concerned with interpreting, interpreting, explaining the text of a work of art.

Researcher M.Nefezov noted that the method of hermeneutic analysis includes such tasks as restoration and preparation of the text, solving problems of authenticity of the text, time of writing, author (other authors' linguistic, literary and historical commentary on the work). sources, character images, and literary assimilations. Many researchers use hermeneutic analysis in the analysis of works of art, some interpret thou approval. In our view, this interpretation interpretation type of analysis leads to the conclusion that the work of art.

Interpretation (Latin interpretation) is a specific explanation of the content, the formal features of a literary work. Interpretation is the reinterpretation of the artistic content of a work through other forms of art or scientific language. For example, the content of a work of art is reinterpreted and explained in the visual arts, graphics, theater, cinema, music and other similar art forms, as well as in literary criticism and literary criticism through the means of scientific logical language. Interpretation is a form of assimilation, rethinking and enrichment of the literary and artistic experience accumulated in human civilization, a manifestation of the meaning and essence of classical works, their eternal existence.

Here, all the recommended types of analysis, as well as all other types available in literature, must be thoroughly studied by the teacher, because he must be able to make full use of the above methods and techniques when analyzing a work of art in literature classes. For example, when analyzing the artistic images in a work, one can use elements that are specific to different types of literary analysis.

The formation of students' reading culture, independent thinking skills, oral and written speech, development of creative abilities on the basis of problematic questions and tasks, enrichment of vocabulary play an important role in embodying the spiritual and moral image of the person. It is closely connected with the development of intellectual potential of students in the general secondary literary education, the formation of artistic and aesthetic thinking, the implementation of the requirements of the STS on building a democratic society, plays an important role in the formation of self-awareness, patriotism, patriotism.

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